

Calibration of an optical microscope

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When a digital camera is installed in the trinocular of an optical microscope it has to be calibrated to provide quantitative information of the samples' dimensions through optical microscopy images.

Figure 1. Picture of the Motic BA310 MET-T optical microscope equipped with an AMScope MU1803 digital camera.

The calibration of the microscope can be carried out by imaging several standard samples with features of well-known dimensions. **Table 1** summarizes the calibration samples employed here.

Figure 2 compares optical images of the test samples acquired with the optical microscope shown in Figure 1 with a 50x objective.

Type of sample	Supplier	Price (€)	Pitch (nm)
DVD	---	---	740
CD	---	---	1600
Grating 600 lines/mm (GR13-0605)	Thorlabs	62.79	1667.7
Grating 300 lines/mm (GR13-0305)	Thorlabs	62.79	3333.3
AMScope test sample (MR095)	AMScope	11.99	10 000
TEM grid G2000	Gilder	44.50 (10/vial)	12 500
TEM grid G1500	Gilder	47.58 (15/vial)	16 500
TEM grid G1000	Gilder	44.50 (25/vial)	25 000
TEM grid G600	Gilder	67.45 (100/vial)	42 000

Table 1. Summary of test samples used to calibrate the optical microscope.

Figure 2. Summary of test samples used to calibrate the optical microscope (all pictures have the same dimensions).

From the acquired optical images one can measure the pitch distance (in pixels) with an image analysis software like ImageJ® or Gwyddion® using the line profile tool or the fast Fourier transform (FFT) tool (see **Figure 3**). **It is convenient to measure as many tracks as possible to reduce the uncertainty!** In samples with a very high density of tracks (e.g. the DVD, the CD or the 600 lines/mm grating) it results very convenient to use the FFT tool. **NOTE: when using the line profile tool be extremely thorough when counting the number of tracks.**

Figure 3. Optical microscopy images of a CD and a DVD used as reference samples to calibrate the optical microscope. The FFT of the images are shown besides the optical image where the period of the tracks can be easily extracted.

Figure 4 shows the relationship between the measured (using a 50x objective) pitch distance between tracks, measured in pixels from the images, and the actual pitch distance provided by the manufacturers.

Figure 4. Relationship between the measured pitch (in pixels) and the actual pitch (in nm) of the standard samples.

The calibration of the objective can be directly extracted from the slope (24.66 nm/pixel in this case). **Figure 5** shows the comparison between the calibration of the different objective lenses of the microscope.

Figure 5. Comparison between calibration measurements with different objectives.

In **Figure 6** we show the linear relationship between the calibration and the objective magnifications. We show this because most of the optical microscope users calibrate a high magnification objective and then they calculate the calibration of the lower magnification objectives by simply multiplying.

Figure 6. Relationship between the magnifications of the optical microscope and the calibration obtained for each one.